

VARIATION OF ABSOLUTE VISCOSITY WITH TEMPERATURE.

ORGANIC SOLUTES IN NON-AQUEOUS SOLVENTS

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The variation of viscosity with temperature of non-electrolytes in non-aqueous solvents has been studied. It has been observed that the simple equation of Andrade, $\log \eta = A + B/T$ is applicable to the most of the systems studied here. The values of the constants A and B of the above equation have been calculated and it has been found that A is the same both in aqueous and non-aqueous media, while B changes from solvent to solvent.

In a previous paper (Chatterji and Bose, this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 39), the variation of absolute viscosity with temperature was studied. In the present communication the same work has been extended to other systems of non-electrolytes in non-aqueous solvents.

EXPERIMENTAL

The method employed is the same as given in the previous paper (*loc. cit.*). The results obtained are given in Table I. The viscosity was determined at four different concentrations and at several temperatures. But on account of brevity of space, the observations at the highest and at the lowest concentrations have only been recorded below. The concentrations given are expressed in g. of anhydrous solute in 100 g. of pure solvent.

TABLE I

Viscosity of solutions at different temperatures.

Solute	Conc.	25°.	30°.	35°.	40°.	45°.	50°.
Solvent = Methyl alcohol.							
Benzoic acid	68.0	0.01311	0.01196	0.010980	0.010140	0.009466	—
	83.0	—	0.013600	0.012500	0.0114700	0.010530	—
Salicylic acid	65.0	—	—	0.010490	0.009732	0.008932	0.008273
	75.0	—	—	0.011180	0.010360	0.009552	0.008818
Phthalic acid	24.6	—	—	0.009160	0.008445	0.007770	0.007180
	33.0	—	—	0.010850	0.010090	0.009326	0.008526
Cinnamic acid	37.5	—	—	0.008910	0.008453	0.007855	0.007246
	50.3	—	—	0.010920	0.010030	0.009163	0.008460
<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid	110.0	—	—	0.018890	0.017270	0.015730	0.014210
	156.0	—	—	0.027730	0.024250	0.022620	0.020260
Succinic acid	19.6	—	—	0.008055	0.007491	0.006981	0.006460
	27.8	—	—	0.009556	0.008870	0.008175	0.007603
Solvent = Acetone.							
Benzoic acid	56.00	0.00755	0.007075	0.006647	0.006278	0.005884	—
	62.5	—	0.007776	0.007283	0.006819	0.006407	—

TABLE I (contd.)

Solute.	Conc.	30°.	35°.	40°.	45°.	50°.	55°.
Solvent == Propyl alcohol.							
Benzoic acid	40.0	0.025310	0.022430	0.019880	0.017700	—	—
	56.0	0.028440	0.024980	0.022060	0.019650	—	—
Salicylic acid	43.0	—	0.022360	0.020120	0.017910	0.016020	0.01438
	54.0	—	—	0.021700	0.019290	0.017220	0.01545
Phthalic acid	10.6	—	0.021330	0.018870	0.016720	0.014880	0.01331
	5.6	—	0.017800	0.016320	0.014570	0.013020	0.01165
Cinnamic acid	18.2	—	0.020660	0.018360	0.016290	0.014520	0.01292
	30.3	—	0.024400	0.021580	0.108880	0.016830	0.01506
<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid	108.4	—	—	—	0.039510	0.034560	0.03018
	78.8	—	—	—	0.030070	0.026320	0.02324
Succinic acid	6.1	—	0.018720	0.016570	0.014920	0.013260	0.01190
	9.8	—	—	0.018880	0.016350	0.014620	0.01313
Solvent == Butyl alcohol.							
Salicylic acid	30.3	—	0.024530	0.021870	0.019510	0.017360	0.01550
	44.5	—	0.027610	0.023750	0.021540	0.019280	0.01725
Phthalic acid	4.9	—	0.023020	0.020330	0.018060	0.016040	0.01432
	7.3	—	—	0.021800	0.019280	0.017120	0.01529
Cinnamic acid	21.2	—	—	—	0.020730	0.018380	0.01638
	15.7	—	0.024800	0.021900	0.019320	0.017120	0.01532
Succinic acid	2.7	—	0.021670	0.019100	0.017040	0.015100	0.01357
	7.8	—	—	—	0.019430	0.017260	0.01541
Solvent == Nitrobenzene.							
Benzoic acid	12.0	—	0.017460	0.016260	0.015030	0.013970	0.01302
	21.0	—	—	0.017460	0.016110	0.014920	0.01393

From the results given in Table I, the following types of curves have been plotted: (1) $\eta-t$, (2) $\log \eta-t$, (3) $\log \eta-1/T$; of these types of curves \log viscosity against $1/T$ gives a more general and clearer approach to linearity like other systems studied in the previous paper. In almost all the systems the plot of $\log \eta-1/T$ gives a straight line, except in a few systems like, methyl alcohol—benzoic acid, methyl alcohol—phthalic acid, methyl alcohol—cinnamic acid, and methyl alcohol—*m*-nitrobenzoic acid, where there is a very slight positive curvature. Hence the Andrade's equation $\log \eta = A + B/T$ (1) is applicable to the most of the systems studied here.

It is observed that in the systems of methyl alcohol and different organic acids the plot of $\log \eta$ against $1/T$ is not a straight line; this may be due to the marked association of the methyl alcohol molecules as compared to the other alcohols of the same series.

From the Andrade's equation the values of the constants A and B have also been calculated. The results obtained are given in Table II.

TABLE II.

Solute.	A .	$B(Q/R)$.	Solute.	A .	$B(Q/R)$.	Solute.	A .	$B(Q/R)$.
Solvent=MeOH.			Solvent=Pr OH.			Solvent=BuOH.		
Benzoic acid	-7.0951	1567	Benzoic acid	-8.0050	2310	Salicylic acid	-8.0640	2320
Salicylic acid	-7.4750	1712	Salicylic acid	-9.4100	2330	Phthalic acid	-9.4710	2448
Phthalic acid	-7.3970	1690	Phthalic acid	-9.4240	2410	Cinnamic acid	-9.5146	2468
Cinnamic acid	-7.7790	1809	Cinnamic acid	-9.6989	2514	Succinic acid	-9.3091	2375
<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid	-8.0660	2020	<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid	-10.106	1700	Solvent=Acetone.		
Succinic acid	-8.1554	1887	Succinic acid	-9.0560	2286	Benzoic acid	-5.8840	1132
						Solvent=Nitrobenzene.		
						Benzoic acid	-7.5790	1816

The value of A for different systems is almost constant and has the same numerical value as those of the systems already studied in the previous paper. If in the equation of Andrade we take the value of T as infinity then $\log \eta = A$, i.e., the viscosity of the infinite temperature is nearly the same in all the systems, aqueous or non-aqueous.

The value of B appears to be the characteristic of the solvent, e.g. for the systems of methyl alcohol it is nearly 1800, for propyl and butyl alcohol it is between 2300 and 2500. This may be due to the presence of CH_2 group in between CH_3 and OH group and thus making the OH group less active.

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